

New Data and Nomenclatural Notes on the Tephritidae (Diptera) of Far East Russia. II

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New Data and Nomenclatural Notes on the Tephritidae (Diptera) of Far East Russia. II. Korneyev V. A. — Species of the tribe Trypetini are taxonomically treated for the forthcoming "Keys to Insects of Far East Russia". *Trypeta anitra* Korneyev, sp. n. and *Morinowotome itoi* Korneyev, sp. n. are described. The following synonyms are established: *Calosphenisca* Hendel, 1914 = *Fusciludia* Ito, 1984, syn. n.; *Acidiella* Hendel, 1914 = *Flaviludia* Ito, 1984, syn. n.; *Hemileophila sibirica* (Portschinsky, 1892) = *H. alini* Hering, 1940, syn. n. = *H. undosa* Ito, 1951, syn. n.; *Anastrephoides matsumurai* Shiraki, 1933 = *A. annulifer* Hering, 1940, syn. n.; *Philophylla marumoi* (Miyake, 1919), = *Euleia basihyalina* Hering, 1951, syn. n.; *Trypeta quaesita* Ito, 1984 = *T. quadrangulifer* Richter et Kandybina, 1985, syn. n.; *T. immaculata* (Macquart, 1835) = *T. digesta* Ito, 1984, syn. n.; *Stemonocera corruca* (Hering) = *Vidalia koreana* Kwon, 1985, syn. n. *Acidiella bipunctata* (Portschinsky), comb. n. (= *Spilographa bipunctata*) = *Shiracidia dilutata* Ito, 1984, syn. n. The new combinations proposed are: *Magnimyiolia quadrinota* (Hardy), comb. n. (= *Myoleja quadrinota*), *Acidiella zephyria* (Ito), comb. n. (= *Flaviludia zephyria*). The genus *Hyleurinus* Ito is resurrected from synonymy. *Chetostoma dilutum* (Zia), *Itosigo bellus* Ito, *Magnimyiolia media* Ito, *Trypeta submicans* Zia, *Hyleurinus kalopanacis* Ito, *Yamanowotome accepta* Ito, *Y. pilosa* Ito, "Dryadodacryma" albicostale Ito, *Pseudhemilea longistigma* (Shiraki), *Angelogelasinus naganensis* (Shiraki), *Morinowotome egregia* (Ito), *Alsangelisca takeuchii* (Ito), *Acidiella pachypogon* (Ito), *A. zephyria* (Ito), *A. issikii* (Shiraki) are newly recorded from Far East Russia. Females of *Yamanowotome pilosa* Ito, *Acidiella obscuripennis* Chen are described for the first time. The lectotypes of *Spilographa bipunctata* Portschinsky and *Spilographa armifrons* Portschinsky are designated.

Новые данные и замечания по номенклатуре Tephritidae (Diptera) Дальнего Востока России. II. Корнеев В. А. — Таксономически обработаны виды трибы Trypetini, включаемые в готовящийся «Определитель насекомых Дальнего Востока России». Описаны *Trypeta anitra* Korneyev, sp. n. и *Morinowotome itoi* Korneyev, sp. n. Устанавливаются следующие синонимы: *Calosphenisca* Hendel, 1914 = *Fusciludia* Ito, 1984, syn. n.; *Acidiella* Hendel, 1914 = *Flaviludia* Ito, 1984, syn. n.; *Hemileophila sibirica* (Portschinsky, 1892) = *H. alini* Hering, 1940, syn. n. = *H. undosa* Ito, 1951, syn. n.; *Anastrephoides matsumurai* Shiraki, 1933 = *A. annulifer* Hering, 1940, syn. n.; *Philophylla marumoi* (Miyake, 1919), = *Euleia basihyalina* Hering, 1951, syn. n.; *Trypeta quaesita* Ito, 1984 = *T. quadrangulifer* Richter et Kandybina, 1985, syn. n.; *T. immaculata* (Macquart, 1835) = *T. digesta* Ito, 1984, syn. n.; *Stemonocera corruca* (Hering) = *Vidalia koreana* Kwon, 1985, syn. n. *Acidiella bipunctata* (Portschinsky), comb. n. (= *Spilographa bipunctata*) = *Shiracidia dilutata* Ito, 1984, syn. n. Предложены новые комбинации: *Magnimyiolia quadrinota* (Hardy), comb. n. (= *Myoleja quadrinota*), *Acidiella zephyria* (Ito), comb. n. (= *Flaviludia zephyria*). Род *Hyleurinus* Ito восстановлен из синонимии. Впервые для Дальнего Востока России указываются *Chetostoma dilutum* (Zia), *Itosigo bellus* Ito, *Magnimyiolia media* Ito, *Trypeta submicans* Zia, *Hyleurinus kalopanacis* Ito, *Yamanowotome accepta* Ito, *Y. pilosa* Ito, "Dryadodacryma" albicostale Ito, *Pseudhemilea longistigma* (Shiraki), *Angelogelasinus naganensis* (Shiraki), *Morinowotome egregia* (Ito), *Alsangelisca takeuchii* (Ito), *Acidiella pachypogon* (Ito), *A. zephyria* (Ito), *A. issikii* (Shiraki). Описываются ранее неизвестные самки *Yamanowotome pilosa* Ito, *Acidiella obscuripennis* Chen. Обозначаются лектотипы *Spilographa bipunctata* Portschinsky и *Spilographa armifrons* Portschinsky.

When preparing the tephritid chapter for the "Keys to Insects of Far East Russia" (Korneyev, Ovchinnikova, in prep.) several new synonyms and names that need to be resurrected from synonymy, and other previously unpublished nomenclatural changes were noted; new undescribed taxa were recognized, and some already known species and their host plants were recorded in Far East Russia for the first time.

An aim of this paper is to point out such improvements and additions to the Russian Far East fauna and to supply them with proper explanations and comments. The present communication covers the subfamily Trypetinae sensu stricto (*i. e.*, only the tribes Trypetini and Carpomyini included). The nomenclature mostly follows Han (1992) in his unpublished thesis and recently introduced by Thompson et al. (1998), with several corrections and improvements that are discussed herein.

The type and other specimens are deposited in the following institutions:

Natural History Museum, London (NHML), Naturhistorisches Museum Wien (NHMW), Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology, Kiev (SIZK), University of Osaka Prefecture (UOP), Zoological Institute of Russian Academy of Sciences, St. Petersburg (ZISP), Zoological Museum of Moscow University (ZMUM).

The following abbreviations are used in the text below:

Amur. — Amurskaya oblast';

Prim. — Primorskiy (before 1965 Ussuriyskiy) Kray;

S. Khab. — South of Khabarovskiy Kray;

S. Kur. — southern Kurile Islands;

S. Sakh. — southern Sakhalin;

Kamenushka — Ussuriyskiy State Reserve, village Kamenushka 40 km SE of Ussuriysk;

Kedrovaya Pad' — Natural Reserve "Kedrovaya Pad'" W of Primorskoye.

FER = frons : eye width ratio (dorsal view);

FR = frontal ratio (= length : width);

HR = head ratio (= length : height : width).

Subfamily Trypetinae

Tribe Trypetini

Anomoia–*Chetostoma* group of genera

Myoleja Rondani

Type species. *Tephritis lucida* Fallén, by original designation.

This genus was known to include 2 Palaearctic species: *M. lucida* (forest zone of Europe, Altai), the Far East *M. sinensis* (Zia). *M. megaloba* Hardy, 1987 described from Papua New Guinea apparently belongs to this genus, too. Recently, Norrbom (in: Thompson et al., 1998) transferred here *Shunraia boninensis* Ito, accepting changes proposed by Han (1992) in his unpublished dissertation, and *Euleia contemnens* Hering, *Pseudosphenicus desperatus* Hering, that were included herein by Hardy (1987) and not transferred elsewhere by Han (loc. cit.).

Another taxon that apparently belongs to *Myoleja*, is *Spilographa caucasica* Bigot, a species of somewhat doubtful identity whose types have not been located; the only species from Caucasus that fits its description is a species closely related to *M. lucida*, but certainly different from the latter.

Females of *Myoleja* differ from the species assigned to other genera of the *Chetostoma*–*Anomoia* group by the aculeus largely and sparsely serrate apicoventrally only.

Although some species of *Myoleja* and *Anastrephoides* Hendel share similar wing pattern and body coloration, they strongly differ by the structure of male and especially female genitalia (see below).

Myoleja sinensis (Zia)

Zia, 1937 (*Anastrephoides*); Chen, 1948; Kandybina, 1966 (*Euleia*); 1977; Foote, 1984 (*Myoleja*).

Material. Prim. Kamenushka, 11.08.1987, ♂ (head lost) (Antropov) (ZMUM); [Partizansk, 14.09.1968, ex *Lonicera*, 4 ♂, 4 ♀ (Kandybina) (SIZK).]

This species was originally described as *Anastrephoides* for it has similar wing pattern. The close relationship of this species and *M. lucida* was first proven by Kandybina (1966; 1977) from larval characters, and then by Han (1992; 1996) and by Korneyev (1995) from the structure of the terminalia.

Anomoia solennis (V. Richter)

Material. S. Sakh.: Novoalexandrovsk, 14.07.1975, 17, 26.07.1986, idem, Tshekhov Mt., h=200 m, Bureya river valley, 21.07.1986, 2 ♂, 2 ♀ (Nesterov); S. Kur.: Kunashir, 24 km NE of Yuzhno-Kurilsk, Dobry Klyuch river, 7.08.1986, ♂ (Kotenko) (SIZK).

The coloration of the abdominal terga is extremely variable, from completely yellowish-brown to largely black spotted. The only difference from *A. vulgaris* Shiraki is the broadly black mediotergite.

Chetostoma Rondani

Type species. *Chetostoma curvinerve* Rondani, by original designation.

The Palaearctic species of this genus were recently keyed by Korneyev (1990). Females of *Chetostoma* differ from the other genera of this group by the aculeus with small and dense serration both apicoventrally and apicodorsally. Since that time Han (1992) has shown that *Euchaetostoma mirabilis* Chen is congeneric with *Chetostoma curvinerve*, and this synonymy is accepted and formally published by Thompson et al. (1998). For this reason, *Ch. mirabile* (Chen) and *Ch. japonicum* (Ito), originally described in *Euchaetostoma* were added to the list of Far East *Chetostoma*. *Sineuleia esakii* Ito, 1960, known only from the holotype ♀ from Kyushu, shares with *Chetostoma* species the short, subquadrate subcostal cell and rather long parastomal setulae, so it is keyed in the latter genus (Korneyev, Ovchinnikova, in prep.); its original combination is being used until its genitalia are dissected and the male is discovered.

Chetostoma dilutum (Zia)

Material. Prim.: Kamenushka, 13.08, 13.09.1987, 2 ♂ (Shatalkin) (ZMUM) (new for Russia).

Chetostoma continuans (Zia)

Material. Prim.: Khasan distr.: Tsukanovo, 15.08.1986, ♂ (Churkin) (ZMUM).

Chetostoma melliculum (V. Richter)

Material. Prim.: Kamenushka, 19.08.1984, ♀, 4.09.1987, ♂ (Shatalkin); Kedrovaya Pad', 26.08.1964, ♀ (Usachev) (ZMUM).

Subtribe Trypetina

Hemileophila Hering

Type species. *Hemileophila alini* Hering, by original designation.

This genus fits near *Platyparea* Lw., especially in the head shape and in the presence of 3-7 frontal setae, but it differs by the katapisternal seta well-developed and by the glans of phallus with two sculptured areas on inner surface of

preputium; female terminalia not examined. Despite its similar wing pattern, the following species is not closely related to *Hemilea* Lw., as was suggested by Han (1992) and accepted subsequently by Thompson et al. (1998), who synonymized *Hemilea* and *Hemileophila*. I am considering the latter to be a valid genus. It shares the head shape, short arista, dark body coloration, shining mesonotum with 2 silvery tomentose vittae and shining convex scutellum with *Platyparea* and seems to be closely related to the latter genus.

Hemileophila sibirica (Portsch.)

Portschinsky, 1892; Hendel, 1927; Zia, Chen, 1938; Chen, 1948 (*Hypenidium*); Richter, 1969; Foote, 1984 (*Hemileophila*); Thompson et al., 1998 (*Hemilea*). — *alini* Hering, 1940 a; Foote, 1984 (*Hemileophila*); Thompson et al., 1998 (*Hemilea*), *syn. n.* — *undosa* Ito, 1951; 1984; Foote, 1984 (*Hemileophila*); Thompson et al., 1998 (*Hemilea*), *syn. n.*

Material. Lectotype *H. sibiricum*: ♂: “*Hypenidium sibiricum*”, [Russia: “Amur, Wladiwostok”] (designated by Richter, 1969) (ZISP) (examined). Holotype *H. alini*: ♂: “Sjaolin, 20.VII 1937, Mandchurei, W. Alin, 1937”, “Type *Hemileophila alini* det. M Hering” (DEI) (examined). Holotype *H. undosa*: ♀: [“Kôrasan, Fukuoka-Provinz, 5. Mai 1934, K. Yamauchi leg.”], (UOP) (not examined). Non-type material: Prim.: Kamenushka, 3, 25.06.1984, 2 ♂ (Shatakin) (ZMUM); Tigrovaja Suchan. distr., 9.06.1927, ♂ (Stackelberg) (ZISP).

Remarks. I was not able to find any significant differences among the specimens assigned to the three mentioned species, except for the variation of size of the light spotlet adjoining R₁ apex and occasionally appearing setae on R₄₊₅ in some specimens from Primorye. For this reason *H. alini* and *H. undosa* are considered as synonyms of *H. sibirica*.

Calosphenisca Hendel

Calosphenisca Hendel, 1914 (type species: *Calosphenisca volucris* Hendel, 1914, by original designation). — *Fusciludia* Ito, 1984 (type-species: *Fusciludia aliquantula* Ito, by original designation), *syn. n.*

Remarks. The concept of the genus *Fusciludia* was expanded by Han (1992), and then accepted by Hancock and Drew (1994), Permkam and Hancock (1995), and Thompson et al. (1998). The species they included herein are rather different, and the genus has become somewhat heterogeneous, that necessitates further confirmation of its monophyly and a full revision.

According to Han (1992), the species of *Fusciludia* can be readily distinguished by the mesonotum shining dark brown to shining black, contrasting with whitish or ivory scutellum and anepisternum. Some species of *Euleia* Walker having shining black mesonotal scutum and ivory scutellum, can be recognized by the anepisterna mostly dark brown, and the species of *Urophora* R.-D. — by the cell cup closed by bowed CuA₂ without extensions along A₁.

When studying a syntype of *C. volucris* it was found to fit near the other species assigned to *Fusciludia*, especially *F. unicuneata* (Hardy). Because *C. volucris* was never rediscovered nor redescribed since its description, the presumed synonymy of *Calosphenisca* and *Fusciludia* was merely omitted.

Calosphenisca volucris Hendel

Hendel, 1914; 1915; Chen, 1948; Hardy, 1977; Thompson et al., 1998 (*Calosphenisca*).

Material. Possible syntype *C. volucris*: ♀: “Kankau (Koshun) Formosa H. Sauter V. 1912 / *Calosphenisca volucris* det. Hendel (NHMW) (examined, but not dissected).

Remarks. This species fits near *Calosphenisca unicuneata* (Hardy), *comb. n.* (= *Myoleja unicuneata* Hardy, 1987, *Fusciludia unicuneata* (Hardy) Permkam

et Hancock, 1995) from Papua New Guinea and Australia, differing by the white coloration of the postpronotal lobes only.

Ito

Type species. *Ito bellus* Ito, by original designation.

Remarks. The type species comprises small reddish-yellow flies with single pair of orbital setae, somewhat reduced wing pattern, and parallel-sided, bluntly tapered, serrate female aculeus (figs 1–2) that resembles the aculeus of Nearctic stem-borers of the genus *Strauzia* R.-D. The neck of spermatheca is very slightly expanded (fig. 3).

Ito bellus Ito

Material. Prim.: Kamenushka, 16, 22, 29.07.1984, 5 ♂, 5 ♀ (Shatalkin) (ZMUM; SIZK) (new for Russia).

Anastrephoides Hendel

Type species. *Anastrephoides gerckei* Hendel, by monotypy and original designation.

This genus comprises three nominal species: *A. gerckei* Hendel described from Astrakhan, and *A. matsumurai* Shiraki and *A. annulifer* Hering from the Palaearctic Far East. These three names, in my opinion, may comprise just one species (see discussion below). *Trypeta tubifer* Walker, assigned to this genus by Chen (1948) as a Chinese species, has been shown to be a species of *Anastrepha* Schiner with erroneous type data (teste Hardy, 1959).

Anastrephoides matsumurai Shiraki

Shiraki, 1933; Chen, 1948; Ito, 1984; Korneyev, 1995. — *annulifer* Hering, 1940 b (*Anastrephoides annulifera*), syn. n. — *gerckei* Hendel, 1927 (possible senior synonym).

Material. *A. annulifer*: China: Holotype ♂, labeled: "Type" (printed on a red-boarded circle), "Type" (printed on red paper square), "Gaolinzsy 2.-8.7.1939" (printed on white paper), "*Anastrephoides annulifera* <sic> ♂ Type det. M. Hering 1939" (handwritten on yellowish paper) (NHML); paratype ♂: with the same data (location not known, probably ZMHB or DEI) (not examined). Non-type materials: China: "Maoershan, 7.07.1940 Manchukuo W. Alin", ♂ (NHML); Russia: Prim.: Khasan distr.: Ryazanovka, 7, 8, 10.07.1989, 3 ♂ (Shatalkin), Spassk, 21.06, 1.07.1961, ♂, ♀ (Zhelokhovtsev) (ZMUM); S. Sakh.: Kholmsk, 24.06.1950, ♂ (Violovitsh) (ZMUM); Novoalexandrovsk, Bureya river valley, 28.06.1974 (Nesterov) (SIZK).

Remarks. This species was completely described and figured by Shiraki (though no sex of the holotype was indicated) and then by Ito, so no redescription is needed; only the structures of terminalia should be added. Male terminalia have not been dissected, and in situ are similar to those of the subtribe Trypetina species; surstyli are long and slender, clearly different of the very short and broad shape in superficially similar species of *Myoleja*; the aedeagus has the praeputium sculptured inside. Female tergo sternum 7 with a tubular, very long apical third, that bears only 2–6 short setulae, and no desclerotized areas at its tip; the eversible membrane bearing numerous tooth-like scales both dorsally and ventrally; the aculeus flattened dorso-ventrally, very long, latero-apically serrate.

The holotype of *A. annulifer* fits very well the descriptions of *A. matsumurai* made by Shiraki and Ito in all the features but the dark apical patch on scutellum. Such patches are rather common in the specimens examined and seem to be merely a postmortal or alive discoloration of the scutellar cuticle. Moreover, Ito (loc. cit.) noted Mandschuria in the distribution range of *A. matsumurai*,

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Figs 1-5. 1 — *Itosigo bellus*, aculeus; 2 — same, apex, enlarged; 3 — same, spermatheca; 4 — *Magnimyiolia media*, aculeus; 5 — same, apex, enlarged.

which was certainly based on the non-type specimen from Hering's collection that Ito received from him, though he never synonymized or even mentioned *A. annulifer* in his papers. Obviously, Ito did not recognize the island and the mainland specimens as two species.

The S- and V-shaped bands are joined through cell r_{2+3} in the paratype of *A. annulifer* (see the original figure in: Hering, 1940 b) and two males from S. Sakhalin, so this appears to be not more than intraspecific wing pattern variation. For this reason *A. matsumurai* and *A. annulifer* are considered to be synonyms.

The taxonomic status of *A. gercke* is unclear. It was known from the single female from "Astrachan" (coll. Gercke, Hamburger Museum), that cannot be located in Wien and therefore is presumed to be destroyed in Hamburg during World War II (B. Merz, pers. comm.). So far, the other known fruit fly specimens from Gercke's collection mentioned by Hering (1940 c) were originated from "Amur", and since the time of description not a single *A. gercke* specimen has been rediscovered from the Caspian area. The description of *A. gercke* is brief, but it appears to fit very closely *A. matsumurai*, except the latter is somewhat bigger (♀ 7.5 mm and 10.0 mm, respectively). The *A. gercke* holotype might be a mislabeled specimen actually originated from Far East Russia, and that this name is the possible senior synonym of *A. matsumurai*.

Magnimyiolia Shiraki

Structures of male terminalia are typical for the Trypetini. *Magnimyiolia quadrinota* (Hardy), comb. n. (= *Myoleja quadrinota* Hardy, 1987) from Papua New Guinea has the face high and the wing pattern mostly dark, and obviously belongs to this genus.

Magnimyiolia media Ito

Material. S. Kur.: Kunashir, 5–7 km N of the Lagunnoe lake, 9.08.1988, ♂, ♀ (Kotenko) (SIZK) (new for Russia).

The aculeus of *M. media* female is not flattened dorso-ventrally, and has the apex tridentate, rather than serrate (figs 4–5).

Genera allied to *Trypeta* and *Acidiella*

This group may be delimited by the following combination of characters: glans of aedeagus always large, spread laterally, the glans with two areas of distinct sculpture (e. g. as it was figured by White, 1988 and Han, Wang et Kim, 1993); female aculei usually flattened dorso-ventrally, wide, with serrate edges posteriorly of ventral lobes and the extreme tip non-serrate.

For most Oriental species which were referred to this group, the generic name *Myoleja* was misapplied by Hardy (1973, 1974, 1977, 1987). It has become clear that *Myoleja* Rond. should be restricted to few species of different shape of aculeus and aedeagus. The species misplaced in *Myoleja* mostly belong to *Philophylla* or related genera. I follow the generic arrangement proposed by Han (1992) in his unpublished thesis and formally published later (Han, Wang et Kim, 1993; 1994 a; 1994 b; Permkam, Hancock, 1995; Hancock, Drew, 1995; Thompson et al., 1998) with some additional improvements.

Philophylla Rondani

Philophylla Rondani, 1870 (type species: *Musca caesio* Harris, [1776], by original designation). — *Hendelina* Hardy, 1951 (type species: *Spheniscus angulatus* Hendel, 1913, by original designation).

Philophylla marumoi (Miyake)

marumoi Miyake, 1919 (*Acidia*); Hendel, 1927 (*Myiolia*); Ito, 1984; Thompson et al. (*Philophylla*). — *inflatus* Shiraki, 1933 (*Pseudospheniscus*). — *basihyalina* Hering, 1951 (*Euleia*), syn. n.

Material. Type: Holotype *Euleia basihyalina*: ♀: NE China: "Type", "Erzendjanjanszy, Mandschurei, 4.VII.1943, Alin S.// *Euleia basihyalina* m. det M. Hering ♀ Type" (NHML) (examined). Non-type: Prim.: Bikin river 22 km higher of Svetlovodnaya river mouth, 14.08.1980, ♀ (Zlobin) (ZISP); Spassk, 9.07.1961, ♂ (Zhelokhovtsev) (ZMUM); Khasan. distr.: Znadvorovka, 16–19.07.1985, ♂, ♀ (Berest); S. Sakh.: Novoalexandrovsk, 21.07.1986, ♂; Tshekhov Mt., 200 m, Bureya river valley, 21.07.1986, ♂, ♀ (Nesterov); S. Kur.: Kunashir, vicinity. of Yuzhno-Kurilsk, Serebrianoe lake, meadow, 8.08.1988, ♂ (Kotenko) (SIZK).

Remarks. This species fits near European *Ph. caesio* Harris, differing by pleurae and femora mostly brown (not wholly yellow); the base of presutural supraalar seta always in the black field (usually in yellow field in *Ph. caesio*). Further comparison with European specimens is necessary to clarify their status and differences. There is a conspicuous variability in the wing pattern of *Ph. marumoi* noted by Ito (1984) who redescribed this species. Examination of the *Euleia basihyalina* holotype shows that it fits well Ito's diagnosis of *Ph. marumoi*. These two species are therefore considered to be synonyms.

Female terminalia as on the figs 6–8.

Trypeta Meigen

Trypeta Meigen, 1803 (type species: *Musca artemisiae* Fabricius, 1794, by subsequent designation of Coquillett, 1910). — *Forellia* Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830 (type species: *Forellia onopordi* R.-D., 1830, by subsequent designation of Duponchel, 1845 (= *artemisiae*)). — *Spilographa* Loew, 1862 (type species: *Trypeta hamifera* Loew, 1846, by subsequent designation of Coquillett, 1910 (= *immaculata* Mcq.)).

Male genitalia as figured by Richter and Kandybina (1985), Hardy (1987) and White (1988).

More than 16 species are recorded currently in Palaearctic. Some are of questionable status.

Trypeta artemisiae F.

Hendel, 1927; Foote, 1984; Ito, 1984; Richter, Kandybina, 1985; White, 1988; Merz, 1994; Thompson et al., 1998. — ? *flavida* Zia, in: Zia, Chen, 1938.

Material. Prim.: Kamenushka, 9.08.1987, ♀ (Shatalkin) (ZMUM); S. Sakh.: Novoalexandrovsk, forest, 19.07.1986 (Nesterov) (SIZK).

Zia (in: Zia et Chen, 1938) described *T. flavida* as having ocellar setae strong, and yellow crossbands of the proximal wing half, with the pterostigmal and anal spots blackish. This character combination commonly occurs both in European and Asian specimens, and I see no way to distinguish *T. flavida* from its description only.

Trypeta trifasciata Shiraki

Shiraki, 1933; Foote, 1984; Richter, Kandybina, 1985; Thompson et al., 1998. — *artemiscicola*: Ito 1984, non Hendel, 1923.

Material. Kamchatka: 18 km NE of Kozyrevsk, 21.07.1985, ♀ (Zlobin); Prim.: Kedrovaya Pad', 30.08.1986, ♀ (Kotenko); S. Sakh.: Novoalexandrovsk, forest, 19.07.1986, ♀ (Nesterov) (SIZK).

This species has the wing pattern similar to that of *T. artemisiae*, differing in the discal and preapical crossbands usually brown-yellow, unbroken, and the ocellar setae conspicuously shorter. *T. artemiscicola* was synonymized to *T. zoe* by Hendel himself.

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Figs 6–8. *Philophylla marumoi*: 6 — aculeus and eversible membrane, ventral view; 7 — same, apex, enlarged; 8 — same, spermatheca.

Trypeta binotata Zia

Zia, Chen, 1938; Foote, 1984; Richter, Kandybina, 1985; Thompson et al., 1998. — ? *beatifica* Ito, 1984.

Material. Prim.: Khasan distr., Ryazanovka 10.06.1989, ♀ (Shatalkin) (ZMUM).

This is a species rather distinctive among those having the broad apical spot, for it has reduced discal and subbasal crossbands with very contrasting dark brown stigmal and anal spots (and usually another one on the R_{2-5} fork) and the preapical crossband only narrowly broken in both females and males. According to Zia (in: Zia, Chen, 1938), the mesonotum anteriorly with black to dark red vittae, sometimes reaching dc level. The specimen before me has 2 broad black submedial stripes at the very anterior margin of mesonotum. Wing pattern of *T. beatifica* looks to fit well the concept of *T. binotata* proposed by Richter and Kandybina (1985), but status of these species, like the most of the Far East *Trypeta* species, needs further clarification under a proper taxonomic revision.

Trypeta submicans Zia

Zia in: Zia, Chen, 1938; Foote, 1984; Thompson et al., 1998. — *zoe*: Korneyev, 1986 (misident.). — ? *zoe*: Richter, Kandybina, 1985, pro parte.

Material. Amur: Zeya, 17.06.1979, ♂ (Shatalkin); Prim.: Kamenushka, 30.05.1989, ♂ (Shatalkin) (ZMUM); S. Sakh.: Urozhaynoe, 6.07.1988, ♂ (Nesterov) (SIZK) (new for Russia).

The Far East species similar to *T. zoe* in having the apical crossband broad, and the male epandrium and female tergosternum 7 black, fits well the description and the figure of *T. submicans*. The latter species, described from females, fits near European *T. zoe* and hardly can be distinguished from its females. But the three males examined fit the description of *T. submicans* very well, showing no sexual dimorphism in the wing pattern at all. For this reason I prefer to consider the eastern specimens to belong to a separate species (or, possibly, a subspecies) that herein is associated with the name *T. submicans*. Further confirmation of its status is necessary.

Trypeta quaesita Ito

Ito, 1984; Thompson et al., 1998. — *quadrangulifer* Richter et Kandybina, 1985, syn. n.

Material. *T. quaesita*: Holotype: ♂: "Japan Hokkaido Kusiro", "Akan, 23 VI.1958 T. Yatsuda" (UOP) (examined, but not dissected). *T. quadrangulifer*: Holotype: ♂: "Кунашир, Дубовое, 20.07.1973, Каспарян" [Kunashir, Dubovoe... Kasparyan] (ZISP) (examined, but not dissected).

Remarks. Both holotypes are very similar in the broad cheeks and postgenae, two dark brown stripes at anterior margin of mesonotum, and the wing pattern, differing by the mediotergite yellowish brown in *T. quadrangulifer* and brownish black in *T. quaesita*. The type localities of the two nominal species are only 150 km apart, and, they are, despite this difference of coloration, certainly conspecific.

Trypeta immaculata (Macquart)

Macquart, 1835 (*Tephritis*); Foote, 1984; Richter, Kandybina, 1985; Thompson et al., 1998. — *hamifera* Loew, 1846 (*Trypeta*); 1862 (*Spilographa*). — *digesta* Ito, 1984, syn. n.

Material. Prim.: Bikin river 22 km higher of Svetlovodnaya river mouth, 14.08.1980, 2 ♀ (Zlobin) (ZISP); S. Sakh.: Novoalexandrovsk, 7-31.07.1986, 2 ♀, Tshekhov Mr., 3.08.1971, 4 ♂, 8 ♀ (Nesterov); S. Kur.: Kunashir, Yuzhno-Kurilsk, vicinity, 5.06.1988, ♀ (Kotenko) (SIZK).

Remarks. Ito noted two characters to distinguish *T. digesta* from *T. immaculata*: 1) r-m proximally of R_1 apex, and 2) dark bands on r-m and dm-cu separated at the hind wing margin. These characters vary, and several specimens in the series from Sakhalin fit very well the description of *T. digesta*. Therefore, the two species are considered as synonyms. They differ from all other *Trypeta* species by the frontal setae somewhat reclinate, not proclinate, sharing this character, as well as the short ocellar setae and larval mining in *Taraxacum* sp. leaves, as well as in other Cichorioidea.

Trypeta anitra Korneyev, sp. n.

Material. Holotype ♀: Prim.: Kedrovaya Pad', 20.08.1984 (Shatalkin) (ZMUM).

Diagnosis. A large yellow species with eyes very high, with broad and long wing that has an unusual, predominantly yellow pattern and the mediotergite with two lateral black spots, yellow medially.

Description. Female. Head (fig. 9) and its appendages yellow. HR = 1 : 1.25 : 1.55. Frons yellow, finely yellowish setulose at the middle and with whitish setulae laterally. FR = 1.6, FER = 0.9. Ocellar triangle black, oc equal to posterior or. Parafacial 0.3–0.5 as wide as flagellomere 1. Pedicel and scape with yellowish setulae; flagellomere 1 rounded at apex, 2.5 times longer than wide, arista shortly pubescent, yellow in basal 1/4. Eye 11 times higher than cheek. Setae dark brown, except genal and postgenal setae slightly brownish yellow. Occiput moderately swollen, covered with yellow setulae.

Thorax yellow, with no tomentosity nor dark patches or strips on mesonotum, with 2 rather small black patches on sides of mediotergite and two black points behind of wing bases. All the setae black; dc slightly behind of asa level; 2 anepisternals, the lower is shorter; katepisternal well developed. All setulae including proepisternal are yellow.

Wing (fig. 10) 2.5 times longer than wide, with yellow pattern and brownish strips on r-m and wing apex. Vein R_{4+5} setulose at most of its length above and with 2–4 setulae below proximally of r-m. The vein r-m is situated slightly distally of dm cell middle. Apical section of M 1.8 times longer than subapical and twice as long as dm-cu. Squamae yellowish, with margin slightly darkened and cilia white.

Legs as typical for genus; yellow with brownish yellow setae and yellowish setae.

Abdomen yellow, with yellowish setae and brown setae. Tergosternum 7 dark yellow, flattened dorso-ventrally, 1.7 times wider its length, 1.5 times longer than tergum 6, and 2.4 times shorter than cell c_2 . Terminalia as on fig. 11–13.

Body length 7.2 mm. Wing length 7.0 mm.

Remarks. This species is similar to *T. oze* Ito from Japan in the mostly yellow, widely spread wing pattern (atypical for *Trypeta*, but commonly occurring in the closely related *Stemonocera* Rond.), and narrow frons and cheeks. It differs from that species by the eyes wider, not incised in profile at hind margin, by the scutum wholly yellow, by the mediotergite mostly yellow, and by the setulae on the mesonotal scutum yellow, not black. The wing of *T. oze* differs from that of *T. anitra* by the dark brown spots at $R_{2.5}$ fork and on apices of sc and cup cells, it is 2.8 times longer than wide; the dm-cu anterior margin more apically produced, the apical section of M twice as long as the subapical, and 2.8 times longer than dm-cu.

Both *T. oze* and *T. anitra* sp. n. have isolated position in *Trypeta* and their generic placement is tentative. To determine their position more precisely the terminalia of both sexes should be examined.

Figs 9-13. *Trypeta anitra*: 9 — head; 10 — wing; 11 — female terminalia (*a* — ventral view; *b* — dorsal view; *c* — scales of eversible membrane, enlarged); 12 — apex of aculeus, enlarged; 13 — spermatheca.

Etymology. The specific epithet is the name of Anitra, the daughter of bedouin's king (H. Ibsen, "Peer Gynt"), and is a noun in apposition.

Cornutrypeta Han et Wang

Cornutrypeta Han et Wang in: Han, Wang, Kim, 1993 (type species: *Trypeta superciliata* Frey, 1935, by original designation). — *Vidalia* auct., pro parte.

The concept of this genus is clearly monophyletic, however the concept of *Trypeta* after exclusion of the *Cornutrypeta* species is paraphyletic. A group of species related to *T. zoe* (with the large apical spot on the wing and short ocellar setae) certainly must include *Cornutrypeta*. Moreover, the presence of 4 fr and 2 or is common for the aberrant female specimens of *T. zoe*, making them hardly different from the females of *Cornutrypeta spinifrons* Schroeder.

Cornutrypeta superciliata (Frey)

Frey, 1935 (*Trypeta*); Han, Wang, Kim, 1993; Korneyev, 1996. — *jibadaua* J. Dirlbek et O. Dirlbeková, 1975 (*Vidalia*) — *jibbidau*: Foote, 1984; Han, Wang, Kim, 1993.

Thus far, the holotype of *Vidalia jibadaua* is the only record of this species in Far East Palaearctic.

Cornutrypeta spinifrons (Schroeder)

Schroeder, 1913 (*Spilogrpha*); Enderlein, 1920 (*Strauzia*); Hendel, 1927 (*Vidalia*); Han, Wang, Kim, 1993; Korneyev, 1996. — *diddiba* J. Dirlbek et O. Dirlbeková, 1975 (*Vidalia*).

Material. Prim.: Khasan distr.: Ryazanovka, 8-10.06.1989, 2 ♂ (Shatalkin) (ZMUM).

Stemonocera Rondani, 1870

Type species: *Musca cornuta* Scopoli, 1772 (by original designation). — *Vidalia* auct., pro parte.

Stemonocera cornuta (Scopoli)

Material. Amur.: Zeya Natural Reserve, 2, 22.07.1978, 2 ♀ (Belov, Ozerov) (ZMUM); S. Khab.: Jewish Autonomic Region, Maly Khingan Mt. rdg., Dichun river, 17.06, 8.07.1981, 2 ♂ (Shatalkin) (ZMUM).

Stemonocera corruca (Hering)

Hering, 1937 a (*Trypeta* (*Vidalia*)); Richter, 1963 (*Vidalia*). — *lucens* Zia in: Zia et Chen, 1938 (*Myoleja*); Chen, 1948 (*Vidalia*). — sp. aff. *lucens*: Korneyev, 1986.

Material. Amur.: Zeya Natural Reserve, 15.08.1982, ♀ (Shatalkin) (ZMUM); S. Khab.: Jewish Autonomic Region, Maly Khingan Mt. rdg., Dichun river, 21.08.1981, ♀ (Ozerov) (ZMUM); Prim.: Kamenushka, 18, 23.08.1987, 3 ♀ (Shatalkin) (ZMUM); Kedrovaya Pad', 30.08.1980, ♂ (Zlobin) (ZISP), idem, 25.08.1964, ♀ (Usachev), Khasan distr.: Tsukanovo, 16.07.1989, ♀ (Churkin) (ZMUM).

Remarks. Han (unpublished data) has studied the type specimens of all the three species and suggested *S. lucens* to be a junior synonym of *S. corruca*.

Stemonocera mica Richter et Kandybina

Richter, Kandybina, 1981; Ito, Tamaki, 1995 (*Vidalia*); Thompson et al., 1998 (*Stemonocera*). — *montivaga* Ito, 1984 (*Vidalia*). — *koreana* Kwon, 1985: 66 (*Vidalia*).

Material. *S. mica*: Holotype: ♂: S. Kur.: Kunashir, Golovnin volcano, 23.07.1973 (Kerzhner) (ZISP). *S. montivaga*: Paratypes: ♂: "Japan Honshiu Bingo:", "Dogoyama 13. VII.1964 T. Yatsuda", ♀: "[Honshiu] Mt. Daisen Totori", with blue paper handwritten labels: "*Vidalia montivaga* Ito Paratype ♂" and "...Paratype ♀" (UOP) (both examined and dissected).

Remarks. All the examined specimens are very similar to those of *S. corruca* except for the frontal process of males much shorter, and for the number of frontal setae is 3 rather than 4. They all are originated from the Kuriles, Sakhalin and Japan whereas *S. corruca* is known from the mainland only. I have not found any characters to separate females of these species. Further study also is necessary to decide if *S. mica* is merely a subspecies or local form of *S. corruca* with the short frontal process. Han (1992, and pers. comm.) suggested that *Vidalia koreana* Kwon is a synonym of *S. mica*, that has male frontal processes somewhat longer, but also with 3 frontal setae, like in typical island specimens. Ito (in: Ito, Tamaki, 1995) synonymized *V. montivaga* with *V. mica*.

Acidia Robineau-Desvoidy

Acidia Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830 (type species: *Tephritis cognata* Wiedemann, 1817, by subsequent designation of Rondani, 1870). — *Epidesmia* Rondani, 1856 (n. praecoc.; nec *Epidesmia* Westwood, 1840 (type species: *Tephritis cognata* Wiedemann, 1817, by original designation). — *Prionimera* Rondani, 1861 (n. nov. for *Epidesmia* Rond.) (type species: *Tephritis cognata* Wiedemann, 1817, automatically).

This genus includes two very similar Palaearctic species, one from Europe and another from Far East, differing in minor details of wing pattern. The name *Acidia* is the valid senior synonym; its senior homonym used within Tunicata only as *lapsus calami* is to be rejected.

Acidia japonica Shiraki

Shiraki, 1933; Richter, 1963; Foote, 1984; Thompson et al., 1998 (*Acidia*); Ito, 1984 (*Prionimera*).

Material. Prim.: Terney, 3-4.08.1937, 1 ♀ (Grunin) (ZMUM); S. Sakh.: Novoalexandrovsk, forest margins, near a river, 14, 17.07, 24.07.1986, 2 ♂, 2 ♀ (Nesterov); S. Kur.: Kunashir, 24 km N from Yuzhno-Kurilsk, 7.08.1988, ♂ (Kotenko) (SIZK).

Acidiostigma Hendel

Acidiostigma Hendel, 1927 (as subgenus of *Myiolia*) (type species: *Myiolia longipennis* Hendel, 1927, by monotypy and original designation). — *Parahypenidium* Shiraki, 1933 (type species: *Hypenidium polyfasciatum* Miyake, 1919, by original designation). — *Shiracidia* Ito, 1984 (type species: *Trypeta s-nigrum* Matsumura, 1916, by original designation).

Han and Wang (1997) show that the concept of *Acidiostigma* should be revised to incorporate all the species assigned to *Parahypenidium* and *Shiracidia* which share extremely broad abdominal sterna and long wing with very long or extremely long pterostigma (except in *A. s-nigrum*, where it is rather short). They have synonymized the three names and transferred several species into *Acidiostigma* that currently enumerates 16 species in Oriental Region and eastern Palaearctic.

Acidiostigma s-nigrum (Matsumura)

*Matsumura, 1916; Hendel, 1927 (*Trypeta*); Foote, 1984 (*Pseudacidia*); Ito, 1984 (*Shiracidia*); Han, Wang, 1997 (*Acidiostigma*). — *takeuchii* Shiraki, 1933; Foote, 1984 (*Pseudacidia*). — *iwatensis* Shinji, 1939 (*Pseuopspheniscus*).

Material. S. Sakh.: Novoalexandrovsk, forest, near the river, 14-17.07.1986, ♂, ♀ (Nesterov); S. Kur.: vicinity of Yuzhno-Kurilsk, 5.08.1988, 2 ♂ (Kotenko) (SIZK).

Aculeus as on the fig. 14. This species was currently redescribed by Han and Wang (1997).

Hemilea Loew

Type species: *Trypeta dimidiata* O. Costa, 1844 (by monotypy).

Remarks. There is no agreement concerning the concept and synonymy of this genus. Hardy (1987) and Han (1992) spread it to include the species assigned to *Hemileophila* Hering, *Pseudhemilea* Chen, *Drosanthus* Hering, *Hemileoides* Rohdendorf, *Hyleurinus* Ito, *Yamanowotome* Ito, and *Dryadodacryma* Ito. Later, this concept was accepted by Thompson et al. (1998), who formally synonymized these genus names with *Hemilea*.

This synonymization has not been accepted herein for certain reasons. *Hemilea dimidiata* Costa and *H. infuscata* Hering are two very closely related vicariant species related to *Trypeta*, because of having shape of surstyli, minute prenisetae and feeding on composite plants like species of *Stemonocera* Rondani, *Cornutrypeta* Han & Wang and *Trypeta* Mg. (Han, 1992). Although other species share the so-called "dimidiate" wing pattern with *Hemilea* were assigned by Han to that genus, they are very different from *H. dimidiata* and *H. infuscata* and hardly share enough characters to make them congeners. The other species considered below as *Hemilea* may belong elsewhere, but apparently not to this genus.

Hemileophila is apparently more closely related to *Oreurinus* Ito (see discussion above).

The species assigned to *Pseudhemilea* Chen, *P. nudiarista* Chen and *P. longistigma* Shiraki, both differ from other species assigned to *Hemilea* by the absence of the genal seta, the character that may indicate their close relationships. *P. longistigma* has surstyli shape very different from those in *H. dimidiata* and *H. infuscata* and apparently is not congeneric with them.

On the other hand, the species known from the literature as "*Hemilea bipars*", sensu Hardy, 1973 & Hardy, 1987 (nec Hardy, 1974) from Laos has very similar shape of the two spermathecae (shorter in *H. longistigma*, longer in "*H. bipars*") and of aculeus; this species is probably congeneric with *P. longistigma*, but nothing is said about its genal seta. The lectotype of *Sophira bipars* Walker is a male (Hardy, 1959), so identity of both "*H. bipars*" sensu Hardy, 1973 and "*H. bipars*" sensu Hardy, 1974 (different in the structure of aculeus and spermathecae) is doubtful.

A complex of the species with the ivory white scutellum, including *Hemilea araliae* Malloch, *H. flavoscutellata* Malloch, *H. atrata* Hardy, *H. lineomaculata* Hardy from Papua and adjacent islands plus *H. quadrimaculata* Hancock and Drew from Southeast Asia share this peculiar character also with *Nemeurinus leucocelis* Ito from Far East Palaearctic. Their close relationship can be hypothesized also from the long wings (synapomorphy?) with 2 costal spots in r_1 (in *N. leucocelis*, *H. atrata* and *H. lineomaculata*), aculeus with minute serration (in *N. leucocelis*, *H. araliae* and *H. lineomaculata*), and the ocellar setae weak.

Besides this, *N. leucocelis* shares the slightly reclinate frontal setae with *H. pulchella*, *H. infuscata* and *Hyleurinus kalopanacis*, but this character may appear also due to convergence. At the same time, not a single Papuan species is said or figured by Hardy as having frontal setae reclinate.

The species assigned to *Dryadodacryma* are very different, and this genus, as it was proposed by Ito, apparently is not monophyletic. "*Dryadodacryma albicostale* Ito is very similar to "*Hemilea*" *bipars* sensu Hardy, 1974, nec Hardy, 1973 & Hardy, 1987 in the structure of aculeus and spermathecae than to any other taxa.

Hemileoides continuus (Ito) (= *Dryadodacryma continuum*) is very close to *H. theodori* Rohd., and was transferred to *Hemileoides* by Korneyev (1995).

The type species of *Dryadodacryma*, *D. fenestratum* Ito is known from the holotype male only, and the concept of this genus is unclear because the most important female postabdomen characters remain unknown.

Males of *Yamanowotome pilosa* Ito are superficially similar to some *Hemilea* s. l. species, but have the aculeus serrate at the very tip only somewhat similarly to that of *Euleia* Walker.

Nemoriludia (recently attributed by Han (1992) to *Magnimyiolia*), superficially resembling species assigned to *Dryadodacryma*, also have the shape of aculeus rather similar to *Euleia* than to *Hemilea*, *Dryadodacryma* or *Magnimyiolia*.

For this reason I consider the genera mentioned above as being separate from *Hemilea*.

Hemilea infuscata Hering

pulchella infuscata Hering, 1937 b; Richter, 1963; — *infuscata*: Sasakava, 1955; Ito, 1984; Kwon, 1985. — *dimidiata*: Zia in: Zia et Chen, 1938; Chen, 1948, nec Costa, 1837. — *pulchella*: Hardy, 1987. — ? *nabiae* Kwon, 1985, presumed synonym.

Material. Prim.: Kamenushka, 27.08.1989, ♀ (Churkin); Spassk, 25.07.1961, ♀ (Zhelokhovtsev) (ZMUM); Tigrovy, 23.05, Sedanka river, 21.06.1963, 2 ♀ (Falkovich) (ZISP); Sedanka, 21.08.1986, ♀ (Kotenko) (SIZK).

This species could be easily recognized among superficially similar Far East species by its shining black abdomen in combination with the frontal setae slightly reclinate, surstyli with posterior lobe very short, subapical preniseta very small, and aculeus with minute and uniform serration posterolaterally. Like in most of *Trypeta*-group species, its larvae are leaf-miners of Asteraceae (*Lactuca laciniata*, *Taraxacum* sp., *T. platycarpum*) (Hering, 1937 b; Sasakava, 1955; Kwon, 1985).

From the description of *H. nabiae* (Kwon, 1985), it looks to be identical to *H. infuscata* Hering, especially considering the slightly reclinate frontal setae, narrowly brown vittate mesonotum and black abdominal terga 3-6. The degree of the cell cua_1 infuscation (formed by blackish microtrichia) varies in the series and depends largely on the angle of view.

The identity of *H. infuscata* sensu Kwon, 1985 needs further confirmation; the brownish yellow color of the abdomen might appear due to discoloration, otherwise it might belong elsewhere.

Hyleurinus Ito

Type species: *Hyleurinus kalopanaxis* Ito, 1984 (by monotypy and original designation).

I synonymized this genus with *Hemilea* Lw. basing only on strong resemblance of their female terminalia (Korneyev, 1995), but neither the shape of spermathecae, nor of aculeus can be considered as synapomorphies. *H. kalopanaxis* and *Hemilea* spp. share also the reclinate frontal setae and short ocellar setae, but the weight of these characters needs further reconsideration. For this, here I suspend use of this synonymy until the proper revision of this group, covering all available types and larger series of specimens, is done.

There is some similarity of *Carpophthoracidia* Shiraki and *Hyleurinus* Ito in the wing pattern (the 3rd section of M is crossed by a hyaline wedge extending from the cua_1 cell). Otherwise they are much dislike, as *Carpophthoracidia* differs by the frontal setae inclinate, the single pair of orbitals, the longer ocellar setae, and the whitish scutellum, the latest also known to occur in *Nemeurinus* and in the *araliae-quadrifasciata* group of species assigned to *Hemilea*.

Hyleurinus kalopanacis Ito

Ito, 1983; 1984 (*Hyleurinus*). — Korneyev, 1995 (*Hemilea*).

Material. S. Sakh.: Novoalexandrovsk, forest edge, at river bank, 14-31.07.1986, 3 ♂, 2 ♀ (Nesterov) (SIZK) (new for Russia).

Larvae mine leaves of *Kalopanax ricinifolius* Miq. (Araliaceae) (Ito, 1984).

Yamanowotome Ito

Type species: *Yamanowotome pilosa* Ito, 1984 (by original designation).

Females of *Yamanowotome* have aculei serrate only at the very apex, somewhat similarly to those of *Euleia*. Beside the two species below, the genus includes *Y. acrotoxa* (Hering, 1938) (= *Euleia acrotoxa* Hering) from Burma, that has wing pattern and venation very similar to those of *Y. accepta* Ito, but the shape of serrate area at the aculeus tip somewhat different than in the compared species or *Euleia heraclei* L. (Han, 1992; Thompson et al., 1998).

Yamanowotome accepta Ito

Ito, 1984 (*Yamanowotome*); Thompson et al., 1998 (*Hemilea*).

Material. Prim.: Kamenushka, 16.07.1984, ♀ (Shatalkin); S. Kur.: Kunashir, Stolbchatyi cape, 29.06.1985, ♂ (Churkin) (ZMUM) (new for Russia).

Yamanowotome pilosa Ito

Ito, 1984 (*Yamanowotome*); Thompson et al., 1998 (*Hemilea*).

Material. S. Kur.: Kunashir: Tretyakovo, 10.07.1985, ♂; vicinity of Mendelejev volcano, 17.07.1985, ♂ (Churkin) (ZMUM); 5-7 km N from the Lagunnoe lake, 9.08.1988, 2 ♀ (Kotenko) (SIZK) (new for Russia).

Description. Female (new). Similar to male in body coloration yellow with two patches of black on the metanotum. In contrast to male, the female has the wing pattern predominantly yellow with a long hyaline spot in the cell br, similar to *Y. accepta*, but having the hyaline mark in the distal third of dm cell open posteriorly, like in the male of *Y. pilosa*. Female terminalia like in *Y. accepta*: tergo sternum conical, apically tapered, so its apical opening is more postero-dorsal rather than posterior, with 6 apicoventral and 2 apicodorsal setae, 2 ventral and 2 dorsal taeniae (both in 1/3 of eversible membrane length), and the posterior 2/3 of the membrane evenly covered with rather small and uniformly blunt diamond-shaped scales. Aculeus narrowly pointed apically, serrate only at its very tip, with smooth postero-lateral edge (figs 15-16). Only 2 strongly sclerotized spermathecae without bulbous expansion of the neck (fig. 17).

Hemileoides Rohdendorf

Type species: *Hemileoides theodori* Rohdendorf (by original designation and monotypy).

The genus includes also *Hemileoides continuus* (Ito) from Japan, previously assigned to *Driadodacryma* Ito, that differs from *H. theodori* by the presence of the second hyaline spot in the cell R_{4+5} apically of dm-cu. Both species differ from the species assigned to *Driadodacryma* by 4 to 5 reclinate frontal setae, rather than 3 pro- or inclinate fr. All the specimens known thus far are females. Another species that shares similar wing venation, pattern and weak ocellar setae, is *Acidiella clarilimbata* Chen from eastern China (Chekiang), known to me only from its original description.

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Figs 14–20. *Acidiostigma s-nigrum* (14), *Yamanowotome pilosa* (15–17) and *Hemileoides theodori* (18–20): 14, 15, 18 — aculeus; 16, 19 — same, apex, enlarged; 17, 20 — spermatheca.

Hemileoides theodori Rohdendorf

Rohdendorf, 1955.

Material. Prim.: Kamenushka, 26.07.1984, ♀ (Shatalkin) (ZMUM).

Remarks. This second of known specimens has 4, not 2 fr, as was stated by Rohdendorf. 1 strong + 1 weak or very weak anepisternal setae. R_{4+5} setulose to r-m. Mesonotum subshining yellow, with one medial and two dorsocentral brownish vittae; dc posteriad of asa. Abdominal terga shining black, except for the 1+2nd and 3rd brownish yellow laterally, black setulose. Sterna all yellow. Tergosternum 7 truncated conical, brownish black dorsally, yellowish brown ventrally, black setulose, 1.5 times longer than tergum 6; aculeus with minute apico-lateral serration (figs 18, 19); 3 short oval, sparsely papillose spermathecae with bulbous expansion of the neck (fig. 20).

"*Dryadodacryma*" *albicostale* Ito

Ito, 1984 (*Dryadodacryma*); Thompson et al., 1998 (*Hemilea*).

Material. Prim.: Kamenushka, 4.08.1987, ♀ (Shatalkin) (ZMUM) (new for Russia).

Remarks. This species certainly is not congeneric with the two species mentioned above; it differs by the 2 strong anepisternal setae; the mediotergite ochreous yellow, abdominal terga yellow to brownish yellow at posterior end, black setulose; the tergosternum 7 brownish-yellow, shining, dorsally convex, apicodorsally with 6 thick and short setae, apicoventrally with 4 longer setae; the eversible membrane with 2 dorsal and 2 ventral taeniae as long as 2/5 of the membrane; dorsal scales are long angular, arranged into 2 submedial stripes; ventral ones are much larger at the middle of the ventral side (figs 21, 22); aculeus heavily sclerotized, with rather large and rounded apico-lateral serration (fig. 23); 3 short oval spermathecae with somewhat expanded, but not bulbous, neck (fig. 24).

Generic position of "*D.*" *albicostale* is unresolved, for the females of the *Dryadodacryma* type species, *D. fenestratum*, are not known. "*D.*" *albicostale* female terminalia looks similarly to "*Hemilea bipars*" sensu Hardy, 1974.

Pseudhemilea Chen

Type species: *Acidiella (Pseudhemilea) nudiarista* Chen (by original designation and monotypy).

The concept of this genus probably depends on the choice of the lectotype that is to be designated from among the syntypes of its type species, that apparently might be heterogeneous. At least the following species fits well the original diagnosis of *Pseudhemilea* for the arista is very short pubescent, genal seta is absent and dorsocentral setae situated posteriad of asa level.

Pseudhemilea longistigma (Shiraki)

Shiraki, 1933; Foote, 1984; Thompson et al., 1998 (*Hemilea*); Chen, 1948 (*Acidiella (Pseudhemilea)*); Ito, 1984; Kwon, 1985 (*Pseudhemilea*).

Material. S. Khab.: the Maly Khingan Mt. rdg., Dichun river, 31.07.1980, ♀ (Ozerov) (ZMUM) (new for Russia).

Remarks. Shiraki has described this species after 4 ♂ from Hokkaido, without selection of the holotype. From his original description, this species could be recognized as having at least 2 rather broad (rarely 3) blackish dorsocentral vittae in combination with the subcostal cell nearly as long as the cell c (= c_2), yellow mediotergite and yellow abdomen; Shiraki clearly noticed that *H. longistigma* (♂) does have the genal seta and figured this character. The specimens

Figs 21–24. *Dryadodacryma albicostale*: 21 — female terminalia, dorsal view (a — scales of eversible membrane, enlarged); 22 — eversible membrane, ventral view; 23 — apex of aculeus, enlarged; 24 — spermathecae.

examined by Ito (1984) and the female before me (♀) seem to be conspecific with Shiraki's specimens, though certainly have no genal seta. It may indicate, that this character is apparently sex dependent. It must be kept in mind, that the expression of mesonotum vittae is probably variable, and that the genus requires careful revision.

Female terminalia as on the figs 25–26. The third spermatheca is reduced, and its remnant is a non-sclerotized dead-end tube.

Nemeurinus Ito

Nemeurinus Ito, 1983; 1984 (type species: *Nemeurinus leucocelis* Ito, 1984, by original designation). — *Syusiroitua* Kwon, 1985 (type species: *Syusiroitua maculipennis* Kwon, 1985, by original designation (= *Nemeurinus leucocelis* Ito).

The type species of both genera certainly are synonyms (Korneyev, 1995). This synonymy was discovered independently also by Han (1992; 1997).

Nemeurinus leucocelis Ito

Ito, 1984; Ito, Tamaki, 1994; Korneyev, 1995; Han, 1997. — *maculipennis* Kwon, 1985 (*Syusiroitua*).

Material. Non-type: Japan: Hokkaido, Sapporo, Ishikari, 19.07.1959, ♂, ♀ (Yano) (UOP). Russia: Prim.: Kamenushka, 30.06, 9.07.1988, 10.08.1987, 2 ♂, ♀ (Shatalkin); Khasan distr.: Ryazanovka, 8.06.1989, ♀ (Shatalkin) (ZMUM); S. Sakh.: Tshekhov Mt., 200–500 m, forest, 28.07.1988 ♀ (Kotenko) (SIZK); S. Kur.: Kunashir, Mendeleyev volcano vicinity, 26–27.07.1985, ♂, ♀ (Churkin) (ZMUM) (new for the mainland Russia and Sakhalin).

Angelogelasinus Ito

Type species: *Acidiella naganoensis* Shiraki, 1933 (by original designation and monotypy).

This genus shows certain superficial similarity to some *Acidiella* (see below) differing in the anterior lobe of surstyli slightly bowed, but never strongly produced inward (fig. 28), and the mediotergite with brown or black spots.

Angelogelasinus naganoensis (Shiraki)

Shiraki, 1933; Foote, 1984 (*Acidiella*); Ito, 1984; Thompson et al., 1998 (*Angelogelasinus*).

Material. Russia: S. Sakh.: Novoalexandrovsk, forest edge at a river, 20.06, 14.07.1986, 2 ♀ (Nesterov) (SIZK); S. Kur.: Kunashir: Yuzhno-Kurilsk, 12.08.1971, ♂, ♀ (Nartshuk) (ZISP); Alekhino, vicinity, 13.08.1988, ♀; Golovnin volcano, 20.08.1988, ♀ (Kotenko) (SIZK) (new for Russia). Japan: Sikoku, Tokushima, Iya Sugeoi, 4, 6.06.1950, ♂, ♀ (Ito) (UOP).

Description. Female. Head (fig. 25) wholly yellow. HR=1.0:1.32:1.48. Frons yellow, with rather long, bowed backward brown setulae. Orbital plates of frons at anterior part with brownish setulae and 3 very long fr, crossing above the middle of frons. Ocellar triangle black; oc well-defined, reaching bases of anterior or by their tips. Antennae yellow. Scape and pedicel bears yellowish-brown setulae; pedicel with a strong light brown seta; 1st flagellomere 2.1–2.4 times longer than wide; arista distinctly shortly plumose, yellow at basal 1/3 and black in the rest. Face grayish-yellow. Facials yellow, 0.3 times as wide as 1st flagellomere. Facial ridge bears rather strong blackish setulae. Cheek 1/8 as high as eye. Genal seta strong, black. Postgenal seta yellowish-brown. Labellum yellow, short, with fine yellow setulae; palpi yellow, not extending beyond the peristomal edge, covered with black setae. Occiput very slightly swollen at the lower part, with yellowish setae; vti and vte strong, long, pvt moderately long, postorbital setae rather strong, ca. as long as pvt. All the setae black.

Figs 25–26. *Pseudhemilea longistigma*: 25 — aculeus, ventral view; 26 — spermathecae.

Figs 27–31. *Angelogelasinus naganoensis*: 27 — head; 28 — wing; 29 — male genitalia, right lateral view; 30 — epandrium and surstyli, posterior view (proctiger removed); 31 — glans of phallus (a — insets show enlarged details).

Thorax yellow, with brownish setulae and black setae. Mesonotum with sparse grayish tomentum of microtrichia and 4 indistinct reddish longitudinal strips. Postpronotal lobes and narrow strip at the upper edge of anepisternum light yellow. Katepisterna without dark patches. Scutellum light yellow. Mediotergite shining black laterally, with a yellow medial strip. All the setae black; dc in line with asa; 3 yellow propleural setae; 2 anepst, the lower is ca 2/3 as long as upper.

Wing hyaline with brown and yellow pattern of partially fused crossbands (fig. 28); the basal hyaline spot in r_{4+5} cell extends into cell dm and often joins with distal hyaline incision in r_1 and r_{2+3} cells; the subapical hyaline spots in r_{4+5} and m cells are also joined. Squamae creamy white, alar squama slightly narrower than the thoracal one, with blackish cilia.

Legs yellow, with black setae and setae.

Abdomen yellowish-brown, with blackish setulae and setae; terga 4-5 with a pair of rather pale brownish spots; tergo sternum 7 yellow to yellowish brown, with sparse black setulae, shorter than terga 5-6 altogether. Aculeus as on figs 32-33; rather narrow and elongate, with the anterior teeth forming 2 rows, but not coming onto ventral surface (as in *Morinowotome* Ito) 0.6-0.7 mm long. Three spermathecae as on fig. 34.

Male is similar to female in all the details, except for the terminalia, and differing by the wing pattern mostly yellow (brownish only in the stigma, at the wing apex, on the dm-cu vein and at the cua1 cell apex). Male genitalia as on figs 29-31.

Body length: female: 7.0-7.5; male: 6.0.

Wing length: 6.0-6.5.

Remarks. This redescription is based upon the series from Sakhalin and Kuriles that fits near the descriptions of *A. naganoensis* by Shiraki (1933) and Ito (1984), except for somewhat larger size and wing pattern being brownish-yellow with the hyaline spots larger and more confluent, and brown flecks on abdominal terga less conspicuous as well as the 7th tergo sternum yellowish brown rather than brown. As these characters show conspicuous variability in the examined series, I consider the specimens from both Kuriles and Japan as extremal color forms of the same species.

Angelogelasinus amuricola (Hendel)

Hendel, 1927 (*Myiolia* (*Acidiella*)); Foote, 1984 (*Acidiella* (s. str.)); Korneyev, 1995; Thompson et al., 1998 (*Angelogelasinus*). — *implicatus* Ito, 1984; Thompson et al., 1998 (*Angelogelasinus*) (presumed synonymy).

Material. Type: Syntype ♀: "Amur, leg. Dörries, 1878-1880", "*amuricola* det. Hendel", "Coll. Hendel", "Type ♀, Marked by D. E. Hardy — 1961" (NHMW) (examined, but not dissected). Non-type: Prim.: Kamenushka, 15.07.1984, 28.07.1983, 2 ♂, 2 ♀; Kedrovaya Pad', 22.08.1980, 2 ♀ (Shatalkin) (ZMUM); Khasan district: Zavadvorovka, forest, 21-25.07.1985, ♀ (Berest) (SIZK)

Remarks. This species was rather completely described by Hendel, but only based on a female.

Wing patterns of the specimens seen during this study were found to vary from that drawn by Hendel to the wing pattern drawn by Ito (1984) for *A. implicatus*. The examined series shows rather wide range of wing pattern variability, but the costal cell never has the medial dark spot, and the outer margin of the cell m always dark brown to dark gray (only the specimen figured by Ito as *A. implicatus* has the large hyaline spot in it touching the outer margin).

Figs 32-34. *Angelogelasinus naganoensis*: 32 — aculeus; 33 — same, apex, enlarged; 34 — spermatheca.

Mediotergite with two lateral spots brown to yellow, same variation is observed in coloration of the tergosternum 7. Male and female are similar in most essential features, including the wing pattern (fig. 35). Genitalia as on figs 36-40.

Figs 35–40. *Angelogelasinus amuricola*: 35 — male wing; 36 — male genitalia, left lateral view; 37 — epandrium and surstyli, posterior view (proctiger removed); 38 — glans of phallus (a — insets show enlarged details); 39 — aculeus; 40 — same, apex, enlarged.

As no Japanese specimens were available during this study, and the series before me is not so big to represent the whole range of variability, I retain the synonymy of the current species and *A. implicatus* only presumed.

Synonymization of *A. amuricola* with *A. obscuripennis* (Korneyev, 1989) was based upon the misidentification of females of the latter species (see below).

Morinowotome Ito

Type species: *Pseudacidia egregia* Ito, 1953 (by original designation).

The three species included here by Han (1992), namely *M. flavonigra* (Hendel, 1927) (= *Myioleja flavonigra*) from Szechwan, *M. minowai* (= *Acidia (Pseudacidia) minowai*) from Taiwan, and *M. egregia* are very similar and may be merely synonyms, at least I cannot find any essential characters to separate them from descriptions only. Because they have both posterior and anterior lobes of outer surstyli small, they do not belong to *Acidiella* Hendel (see below). The only character that is the synapomorphy of the two species below and apparently of *Morinowotome* in whole, is the presence of 5–25 blunt denticles on sides of the ventral surface of aculeus at the level of ventral lobes (figs 41–44).

Morinowotome egregia (Ito)

Ito, 1953 (*Pseudacidia*); 1984: 196.

Material. Paratypes: ♂, ♀: Japan: "Kamikoti 17.VII.1951 A. Mutuura", "Paratypus *Pseudacidia egregia* Ito" (on greenish paper) (UOP) (the female dissected). Non-type specimens: Russia: Prim.: Bikin river 22 km higher of Svetlovodnaya river mouth, 14–19.08.1980, 3 ♀ (Zlobin) (ZISP); S. Sakh.: Novoalexandrovsk, forest, 5, 14, 17.07.1986, 4 ♂, 3 ♀; Bureya river valley, 31.07.1986, ♂ (Nesterov); idem, 26.07.1988, ♀ (Kotenko) (SIZK) (new for Russia).

For description of this species see Ito (1984). Aculeus with minute and rather numerous serration laterally and 25–30 denticles at the middle on the ventral surface on each side (fig. 41–42).

Morinowotome itoi Korneyev, sp. n.

Material. Holotype ♀: Prim.: Khasan distr.: Ryazanovka, 11.06.1989 (Shatalkin) (ZMUM).

Description. Female. Head (fig. 46) wholly yellow. HR = 1.0 : 1.36 : 1.56. Frons yellow, with reclinate, rather long brown setulae. FR = 1.3. FER = 1.4. Orbital plates of frons at anterior part with blackish setulae and 3–4 long fr, crossing above the middle of frons. Lunula deeply incised. Ocellar triangle black; oc well-defined, 2.5 times as long as ocellar triangle. Antennae yellow. Scape and pedicel bear yellowish-brown setulae; pedicel with a strong light brown seta; 1st flagellomere 2.3 times longer than wide; arista distinctly shortly pubescent, yellow at basal 1/3 and black in the rest, its rays 1–1.5 times longer than its base width. Face grayish-yellow. Facials yellow, 0.4 times as wide as flagellomere 1 and linear in profile. Facial ridges bear rather strong blackish setulae. Eye vertical elongate, slightly tapered downward. Cheek 1/7 as high as eye. Genal seta strong, black. Postgenal seta yellowish-brown. Labellum yellow, short, with fine yellow setulae; palpi yellow, not extending beyond the peristomal edge, covered with black setulae. Occiput very slightly swollen at the lower part, with yellowish setulae; vti and vte strong, long, pvt moderately long, postorbital setulae rather strong, ca. as long as pvt. All the setae black.

Thorax yellow, with brownish setulae and black setae. Mesonotum with sparse grayish tomentum of microtrichia. Postpronotal lobe and narrow strip at the upper edge of anepisternum light yellow. Katepisternum without dark patch.

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Figs 41-47. *Morinowotome egregia* (41-42) and *M. itoi*, sp. n. (43-47): 41, 43 — aculeus; 42, 44 — same, apex, enlarged; 45 — spermatheca; 46 — head; 47 — wing.

Scutellum light yellow. Mediotergite shining black laterally, with a yellow medial strip. All setae black; dc in line with asa; 3 brown proepisternal setulae; 2 anepisternals, the lower is ca 0.5 as long as upper.

Wing hyaline with a brown and yellow pattern of partially joined crossbands and three dark gray patches: on humeral vein, on R_{2+5} fork, and on transverse portion of vein CuA_2 between the cells cup and cu_{a1} (fig. 47). Squamae creamy white, alar squama slightly narrower than thoracal one, with blackish cilia.

Legs yellow, with black setae and setulae.

Abdomen yellowish-brown, with blackish setulae and setae; terga 4–5 with a pair of brownish spots; tergosternum 7 yellow, with sparse black setulae, shorter than terga 5–6 together. Aculeus as on fig. 43–44; largely serrate, 0.75 mm long. Three ovate spermathecae with bulbous neck as on fig. 45.

Body length: 5.5.

Wing length: 4.8.

Male unknown.

Remarks. This species is similar to *M. egregia* in the wing pattern and the aculeus with the 5–6 denticles on the ventral side, differing by the head higher, the fronto-facial angle rounded and the aculeus having ca. 20–25 larger denticles on each side of its postero-lateral edge rather than 40–50 small ones. The head and eye shape and the wing pattern are also very similar to those of *Alsangelisca takeuchii* (Ito), but the latter species can be easily distinguished by always 2, not 3 or 4 frontal setae, as well as the aculeus lacking any serration (see below).

Etymology. Named after Professor Emeritus Dr. Syusiro Ito (University of Osaka Prefecture), in recognition of his contributions to the study of Palaearctic fruit flies.

Alsangelisca Ito

Type species: *Philophylla takeuchii* Ito, 1951 (by original designation and monotypy).

An aberrant monotypic genus certainly belonging to the group of genera allied to *Trypeta*, and apparently related to the previous genus, but differing by the presence of 2 frontal setae only, the large granulate median sclerite of the phallus (Han, 1992), and the aculeus completely lacking any serration (figs 48–49). Three ovate spermathecae with bulbous neck as on fig. 50.

Alsangelisca takeuchii (Ito)

Material. Prim.: Kamenushka, 18.08.1984, 19.08.1989, 2 ♀ (Shatalkin, Churkin) (ZMUM) (new for Russia).

Remarks. Han (1992) mentioned Sakhalin in the list of distribution, but said nothing about this information source.

Figs 48–50. *Alsangelisca takeuchii*: 48 — aculeus; 49 — same, apex, enlarged; 50 — spermatheca.

Acidiella Hendel

Acidiella Hendel, 1914 (type species: *Myolia (Acidiella) longipennis* Hendel, 1914, by original designation). — *Tetramyolia* Shiraki, 1933 (type species: *Tetramyolia sapporensis* Shiraki, 1933, by original designation). — *Pseudacidia* Shiraki, 1933 (type species: *Acidia (Pseudacidia) issikii* Shiraki, 1933, by original designation). — *Matsumuracidia* Ito, 1949 (type species: *Matsumuracidia mira* Ito, 1949, by original designation (= *Acidia kagoshimensis* Miyake, 1919)). — *Longiusculala* Ito, 1984 (type species: *Acidia maculata* Shiraki, 1933, by original designation). — *Pogonangelus* Ito, 1984 (type species: *Pogonangelus pachypogon* Ito, 1984, by original designation). — *Ihekaze* Ito, 1984 (type species: *Acidiella diversa* Ito, 1952, by original designation). — *Flaviludia* Ito, 1984 (type species: *Flaviludia zephyria* Ito, 1984, by original designation), syn. n.

Diagnosis. Head without appendages, fr : or = 3 : 2, ocellar setae longer, than posterior orbital setae, postgena slightly to strongly swollen, thorax rufous, pleurae never darkened, mediotergite always shining yellow to yellow brown; surstyli lacking posterior lobe, but with large anterior lobe strongly produced inward (synapomorphy).

Remarks. The current concept of the genus was refined by Han (1992) in his unpublished thesis, and the synonymy he proposed, are formally published by Thompson et al. (1998). This concept is accepted herein and, moreover, includes the genus *Flaviludia*, been out of Han's consideration, and later redefined by Korneyev (1995). All the species previously placed to *Flaviludia*, share same wing pattern and yellow mediotergite, and two of them have surstyli with the anterior lobe strongly expanded inward; the type species of *Flaviludia*, is known from females only.

Acidiella longipennis Hendel

Hendel, 1914; 1915; Hering, 1938; Hardy, 1977; Ito, 1984; Korneyev, 1995; Thompson et al., 1998 (*Acidiella*); Chen, 1948 (*Acidiella (Acidiella)*); Hendel, 1927; Shiraki, 1933 (*Myolia (Acidiella)*); Hardy, 1987 (*Myoleja*).

Material. China: Taiwan [Tainan, 04.1910], 7 ♂ (head of one specimen is missed) and ♀ labeled: "Formosa I Sauter R.", "Coll. Oldenberg", "*Acidiella longipennis* Hend. det. H K Munro 1932" (DEI) (examined and dissected).

Descriptions by Shiraki, Ito and Hardy are quite complete, and only the following characters should be added: scutellum short, convex, pleurae are stained-brownish dotted; in some specimens also abdominal tergum 3 with a pair of brown spots; wing pattern in this series rather constant; second costal cell length (c) is 1.15–1.30 mm (average 1.20); the 4th (apical) section of M is 2.8–3.5 (average 3.03) times as long as the subapical one; wing 2.5–2.7 times longer than wide.

Wing length 5.6–6.1 (average 5.9).

Male and female terminalia were figured by Korneyev (1995).

Length of aculeus 0.53 mm.

Acidiella obscuripennis Chen

Chen, 1948; Foote, 1984 (*Acidiella*); Korneyev, 1995 (*Angelogelasinus*). — *amuricola*: Korneyev, 1989 (*Acidiella*) (misident.)

Material. Prim.: Kamenushka, 30.06, 16–19.07, 1–5.08.1984, 14 ♂, 5 ♀ (Shatalkin) (ZMUM, SIZK).

Redescription. Male. Head (fig. 51) light yellow; eye 5 times higher than cheek; face shorter than frons. Thorax and legs completely yellow, except two dots posterior of wing bases; mediotergite shining yellow; propleural setulae and all the setae black. Wing dark brown, light brown only at postero-basal

corner (fig. 52). Abdomen shining yellow except for 5th tergum and terminalia black; abdominal setulae black. Epandrium dark brown; surstyli with large anterior lobe directed inward, and no posterior lobe (fig. 56, 57).

Female similar to male, differing by spotted wing pattern (fig. 53) and by completely yellow abdomen and terminalia (fig. 59-61).

Body length of male 4.5-5.0 mm, of female 4.7-5.4 mm.

Remarks. Korneyev (1995) suggested to place this species into *Angelogelatinus* Ito, because of superficial similarity of the female wing pattern to the species of the latter genus. However, the wholly yellow mediotergite and shape of its male genitalia shows that it certainly belongs to *Acidiella*.

Figs 51-55. *Acidiella obscuripennis* (51-53) and *A. sp. n.* near *sepulcralis* (54-55): 51, 54 — head; 52, 53, 55 — wing (52 — male, 53 — female).

Figs 56-61. *Acidiella obscuripennis*: 56 — male genitalia, left lateral view; 57 — epanthrium and surstyli, posterior view; 58 — glans of phallus (a — insets show enlarged details); 59 — eversible membrane of ovipositor (a — ventral; b — dorsal view; c, d — scales, enlarged); 60 — aculeus; 61 — spermatheca.

Acidiella pachypogon (Ito)

Ito, 1984 (*Pogonangelus*) (♂); Thompson et al., 1998 — *assimilis* Kwon, 1985 (*Pogonangelus*) (♀).

Material. Prim.: Kamenushka, 25.08.1989, ♀ (Churkin) (ZMUM) (new for Russia).

Remarks. Head and wing pattern as on figs 62–63. Terminalia not dissected; aculeus exposed, with minute lateral serration, similar to that of *Trypeta* and other genera of this group.

Figs 62–63. *Acidiella pachypogon*, female: 62 — head; 63 — wing.

Acidiella angustifascia (Hering)

Hering, 1936; Zia, Chen, 1938 (*Myiolia*); Kandybina, 1966; 1977; Foote, 1984 (*Acidiella*); Korneyev, 1995; Thompson et al., 1998 (*Flaviludia*).

Material. S. Khab.: Khabarovsk, vicinity, ex fruits of *Eleutherococcus senticosum* (Araliaceae), 13.09.1959, 2 ♂, 2 ♀ (Sheldeshova) (SIZK; ZISP); Prim.: Sikhote-Alin, Vangou, 16, 17–20.08.1911, ♂, ♀ (Pereleshina) (ZMUM).

Remarks. This species, as well as the three following, have the mediotergite ochreous yellow, ocellar setae not longer than anterior orbitals, and the wing pattern similarly striate, like in *A. zephyria* (Ito), that is the type species of *Flaviludia* Ito. For this reason these species were transferred to the latter genus (Korneyev, 1996), but current study shows that *A. angustifascia* has the surstylus anterior lobe typical for *Acidiella* (figs 64–65), as well as *A. echinopanacis* Kandybina (see: Kandybina, 1966). Although males of *A. zephyria* are still unknown, this complex of species is transferred herein to *Acidiella*.

A. angustifascia differs from closely related species by the pale wing pattern of ochreous and light brown crossbands, relatively large and broad wings (WL > 4.5 mm), and by the tergosternum 7 and male genitalia yellowish. The very apex of the aculeus is conspicuously shorter, than the distance between the apices of the last lateral teeth (figs 67–68).

Figs 64–69. *Acidiella angustifascia*: 64 — epandrium and surstyli, posterior view (proctiger removed); 65 — male genitalia, left lateral view; 66 — glans of phallus (a — insets show enlarged details); 67 — aculeus; 68 — same, apex, enlarged; 69 — spermatheca.

Acidiella angustifascia ?

Material. Prim.: Kamenushka, 16.07.1984, ♀ (Shatalkin) (ZMUM).

Remarks. This specimen has the mediotergite yellow and the tergosternum 7 black; though the latter is unicolor, it just may be full of a putrid content of abdomen; the terminalia are not dissected, but aculeus exposed, and its apex is as in the other examined specimens of *A. angustifascia*.

Acidiella zephyria (Ito), comb. n.

Ito, 1984; Korneyev, 1995; Thompson et al., 1998 (*Flaviludia*).

Material. Prim.: Kamenushka, 27.08.1987, ♀ (Shatalkin) (ZMUM) (new for Russia).

Remarks. This species is known from the holotype female from Japan, and the second female specimen from Russian Far East. They both share moderately long (WL=4.5–4.8) and not apically narrowed wing with the dark brown, rather contrast pattern (see Ito, 1984), and the tergosternum 7 yellowish. The very apex of aculeus was broken off during dissection (fig. 70–71), but on the picture re-composed of two pieces it looks certainly longer, than that in *A. angustifascia* (fig. 68–69).

This species fits closely to *A. angustifascia*, differing in the shape of the aculeus apex and the wing pattern.

Acidiella echinopanacis Kandybina

Kandybina, 1966; 1977; Foote, 1984 (*Acidiella*); Korneyev, 1995; Thompson et al., 1998 (*Flaviludia*).

Material. Prim.: Kievka, 12.09.1980, ♂ (Shatalkin) (ZMUM).

Remarks. Male genitalia of this species figured by Kandybina (1966: fig. 23), clearly shows this species to belong to *Acidiella*. Larvae in fruits of *Echinopanax elatum* Nakai (Araliaceae) (Kandybina, 1966). This species differs from the closely related species (*A. angustifascia* and *A. zephyria*) by the smaller size (WL < 4.5), the wing apically conspicuously elongate and the tergosternum 7 shining black. Female terminalia are not examined.

Acidiella issikii (Shiraki)

Shiraki, 1933; Foote, 1984; Ito, 1984; (*Pseudacidia*); Thompson et al., 1998 (*Acidiella*). — *circumvaga* Ito, 1984 (*Pseudacidia*), presumed synonym.

Material. Prim.: Khasan district: Kedrovaya Pad', 21.08.1964, 23.08.1980, 2 ♀ (Usachev; Shatalkin); Khasan distr.: Ryazanovka, 9–10.06.1989, 2 ♂, ♀ (Shatalkin) (ZMUM) (new from Russia).

Figs 70–71. *Acidiella zephyria*: 70 — aculeus; 71 — same, apex, enlarged.

Figs 72–76. *Acidiella issikii*: 72 — epandrium and surstyli, posterior view (proctiger removed); 73 — male genitalia, left lateral view; 74 — glans of phallus; 75 — aculeus; 76 — same, apex, enlarged.

Remarks. This species was described from Korea, and is based on the holotype female. Ito (1984) described *Pseudacidia circumvaga* from a couple of specimens from Kyûsyû that fits very near *Ps. issikii*, except for the hyaline spot in the cell br situated at the middle of the cell, but not in its apical quarter. The specimens from the Far East Russia examined during this study fit close descriptions of the both species, showing intergrading variability in the wing pattern, including the position of the spot in the br cell. All the examined females have similarly serrated aculeus (figs 75–76), and the specimens listed above are certainly conspecific. But synonymization of the two names is still pending until more material is available.

Generic placement of this species is somewhat questionable. First, it has the anterior lobe of surstylus moderately extended medially (but conspicuously less, than in *A. longipennis*). Furthermore, it has the mediotergite largely black, and the posterior lobe of surstylus less reduced, than in all the species mentioned above (fig. 72–73).

Therefore, *P. issikii* is placed here only tentatively, and as it is the type species of *Pseudacidia* Shiraki, we accept Han's opinion and consider the two generic names as synonyms tentatively, too. The subsequent revision the species assigned to *Acidiella* (Han, Wang, in preparation) must solve this problem in a proper way.

Acidiella sp. near *sepulcralis* Hering

Material. Prim.: Bikin river 22 km higher of Svetlovodnaya river mouth, 14.08.1980, ♂ (Zlobin) (ZISP).

Remarks. This species fits near *Acidiella sepulcralis* Hering, 1938 from northern Burma by the wing pattern (fig. 55) broadly ochreous and the mediotergite yellow, differing by the frons wider (FR=0.9; FER=1.9) and genae higher (1/3 of eye height) (fig. 54). Study of additional material is needed for more precise determination of this species.

Acidiella bipunctata (Portschinsky), comb. n.

Portschinsky, 1892; Foote, 1984 (*Spilographa*). — *dilutata* Ito, 1984 (*Shiracidia*), syn. n. — *spinifera* Hering, 1938 (*Pseudacidia*), presumed synonym. — *yasumatsui* Ito, 1949; 1984 (*Pseudacidia*), presumed synonym. — *disjuncta* Ito, 1953; 1984 (*Pseudacidia*), presumed synonym.

Material. *S. bipunctata*: Lectotype (here designated): ♀, labeled: "*Spilographa bipunctata* ♀" (handwritten by Portschinsky with ink on yellowish paper) and the latest handwritten label "Holotypus ♀ / *Spilographa bipunctata* Portsch." on red paper (ZISP) (examined, but not dissected). *Ps. yasumatsui*: Paratype ♂: Japan: "(Satsuma) Kagoshima 16-IV-1962 A. Nagatomi", "Paratypoid ♂ *Pseudacidia yasumatsui* Ito" (UOP) (examined, but not dissected). *S. dilutata*: Holotype ♀: [Japan: Honsyû, Tokugô-tôge, 13.07.1939] (UOP) (examined, but not dissected). Non-type: S. Sakh.: Moneron Island, 8.07.1949, ♀ (Gusev); S. Kur.: Kunashir, Mendeleev volcano, 4.07.1989, (Churkin) (ZMUM).

Redescription. Female. Head (fig. 77) brownish-yellow; HR = 1: 1.2: 1.4. Frons wide, subquadrate, nearly twice as wide as eye (upper view); FR = 0.8–1.1; FER = 1.7–2.1. Frons and face in profile meet at right or slightly acute angle; eyes small, genae 0.4 as high as eye; occiput swollen, ca. 0.5 of eye length. Chaetotaxy of head complete, 3 (–5) fr, 2 or. Ocellar setae moderately developed, as long as, or slightly shorter than anterior orbitals.

Thorax, including mesonotum, pleurae and mediotergite brownish-yellow, two black dots behind the wing bases. Thoracal chaetotaxy complete; 4–6 black proepisternal setulae; dc behind asa level; 4 scut, 2 subequal anepst; 1 kepst; 1 anepm.

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Figs 77–81. *Acidiella bipunctata*: 77 — head (lectotype); 78 — wing (lectotype); 79 — aculeus; 80 — same, apex, enlarged; 81 — spermathecae.

Wing without modifications; vein R_{4+5} setulose to r-m above, the latter is beyond R_1 end, and distally of dm cell middle. Wing pattern (fig. 78) brownish yellow, conspicuously variable: the hyaline crossband between r-m and dm-cu either whole or broken into 2–4 hyaline spots; the hyaline spot in the r_{4+5} cell isolated or, commonly, broadly joined to the hyaline area in m.

Abdomen brownish-yellow. Tergosternum 7 dark brown to black, rather short, completely sclerotized apically. Aculeus very slightly compressed dorso-ventrally, not serrate, covered with sparse blunt spinules on outer surface of aculeus, as well as on the inner surface of oviprovectro (figs 79–80); 3 spermathecae with non-expanded necks, as on fig. 81.

Body length of female 7.0–8.5 mm. Wing length 6.7–7.5 mm.

Male unknown, but it is believed that the males described by Ito (1984) as *Pseudacidia yasumatsui* Ito and *P. disjuncta* Ito are actually the males of this species. They are similar to female in the head shape, wing pattern and body coloration. Fore femur with a row of spur-like setae ventrally. *P. spinifera* Hering from Myanma share this character, as well as the similar wing pattern and comparatively large size, and might belong here. Male genitalia not dissected.

Remarks. This species can be recognized among Far East Russian Trypetini by the combination of high gena, swollen postgena, shining yellow mediotergite, dark brown to black tergosternum 7. As far as the range of chaetotaxy and wing pattern variation is not examined on larger series, it is possible, that there is a complex of closely related species that fits this diagnosis in Eastern Asia.

The shape of aculeus distinguishes this species from other species of *Acidiella*, therefore its generic placement is based mostly on having the mediotergite shining yellow and the wing pattern similar to that of *A. issikii* and, like in the latter species, is tentative. There are short ventral spinulae on forefemur of *Acidiostigma s-nigrum* males (2 rows!), but their relationship to *A. bipunctata* are not understood.

Vidalia R.-D.

Vidalia Robineau-Desvoidy 1830 (type species: *Vidalia impressifrons* Robineau-Desvoidy 1830, by monotypy). — *Pseudina* Malloch, 1939 (type species: *Pseudina bululoae* Malloch, 1939, by original designation). — *Sinaida* Hering, 1940 c (type species: *Sinaida alini* Hering, 1940 c, by original designation), syn. n..

This genus was recently revised by Han, Wang and Kim (1993; 1994 a; 1994 b) under the name *Pseudina*. Hancock and Drew (1995) discussed the identity of *Vidalia impressifrons* R.-D., the type species of the genus.

Vidalia armifrons (Portschinsky)

armifrons Portschinsky, 1892 (*Spilographa*); Hendel, 1927; Chen, 1948; Ito, 1984; Han, Wang and Kim, 1994 a; Korneyev, 1995 (*Pseudina*) (males). — *alini* Hering, 1940 c (*Sinaida*); Han, Wang and Kim, 1994 a (*Pseudina*) (females). — *Sinaida* sp.: Ito, 1985; 1986 (males and females).

Material. Type: *S. armifrons*: Lectotype ♂ (on a micropin pinned into a piece of cork closer to a general pin) and paralectotype ♂ (on a micropin pinned farther from the pin, wings are partly broken off), with labels handwritten with ink on white paper: “*Spilographa armifrons*”, “Siberia (Raddeuka)” (= S. Khab.: Jewish Autonomic Region, Radde), small white paper square, latter handwritten label on red paper “Syntypus / *Spilographa armifrons* Portsch.”; designated here, with the handwritten labels on red paper “Lectotypus ♂ / *Spilographa armifrons* Portsch. / des. V. Korneyev, 6.02.1986”, and “Paralectotypus / ...”, respectively (ZISP) and figured by Korneyev (1995: fig. 5). *S. alini*: Holotype ♀: CHINA: “Type” (printed on a red-boarded paper circle), “Type” (printed on red paper square) “Charbin, Mandshurei, Gaolinsy, 25.05.1940 (W. Alin)” and ♀ with the same data labeled as “Paratype” (printed on

yellow-boarded paper circle), but not mentioned in the original description and actually not a type specimen (NHML). Non-type material. S. Khab.: Jewish Autonomic Region, Maly Khingan Mt. rdg., Dichun river, 17.06.1981, ♂ (Ozerov); Prim.: Kamenushka, 14.06.1981, ♂ (Shatalkin) (ZMUM).

Redescription. Male (description is based upon the lectotype of *Spilographa armifrons* with the comments on variability in other specimens). Head yellow. HR = 1.0:1.43:1.57. Orbital plates of frons at anterior part with short blackish setulae, and at posterior 2/3 of their length 3 processes bears one rather short and 2 very strong setae. 1 to 2 weaker frontal setae are located behind of these processes. One orbital seta inside of them. Ocellar triangle black; ocellar well-defined, 2.5 times as long as ocellar triangle. Frons yellow, with very sparse brown setulae. Orbital plates of frons, including their projections, with numerous brownish spots and light brown setulae. Antennae yellow. Scape and pedicel bears blackish setulae; pedicel with a strong black seta; 1st flagellomere 2.0-2.2 times longer than wide; arista shortly setulose, brownish-yellow at basal third and black in the rest. Face grayish-yellow. Facials yellow, 0.5 times as wide as 1st flagellomere; facials and falcellae bear rather strong blackish setulae. Cheek 0.2 as high as eye. Genal seta strong. Labellum yellow, short, with fine yellow setulae; palpi yellow, not extending beyond peristomal edge, covered with black setulae. Occiput slightly swollen at the lower part, with brownish spots and blackish setulae; vti and vte strong, long, pvt moderately long, postorbital setulae rather thin, ca. 0.5 as long as pvt. All the setae black.

Thorax brownish-yellow, with setulae and setae brownish to black. Mesonotum with sparse grayish tomentum of microtrichia and 4 blackish longitudinal strips (sometimes indistinct) reaching level of dc (medial pair) and of pa (lateral pair). Postpronotal lobes and narrow strip at the upper edge of anepisternum light yellow. Katepisterna without dark patches. Scutellum light yellow, slightly flattened above. Mediotergite shining, with two black patches. All the setae black; dc in line with asa; 3 propleural setulae; 2 anepst.

Wing hyaline with a rather variable pattern of partially joined crossbands: the lectotype has subapical crossband widely fused with discal crossband at the most width of cell dm, and an apical hyaline spot covering the most of cell r_{4+5} , whereas in some other specimens above mentioned bands are separated in dm with a hyaline spot that covers most of its width, and apical hyaline spot in r_{4+5} is very small. Vein R_{4+5} setulose above to r-m. Process of cell cup extends slightly beyond the line of bm-cu crossvein. Squamae narrow, whitish; alar much narrower than thoracal one, with narrow creamy to brown border and cilia yellowish to blackish.

Legs yellow, with black setae and setulae.

Abdomen yellowish-brown, with blackish setulae and setae; it is darker in Portschinsky's specimens, in the specimens from Dichun and Kamenushka lighter, with a pair of large black spots on tergum 5, those are concolored with surrounding area in Portschinsky's specimens. Epandrium dark brown to black, not dissected for study. Surstyli rather long, yellow; cerci elongate.

Female (description is based upon *Simaida alini* type specimens). Similar to male. Head non-modified; HR = 1.0: 1.25: 1.52. Frons subquadrate, rather dense setulose at median third of its length and with some setulae above the lunula; FR = 0.94; 1 or, 4 fr (in all the known specimens), anterior and especially posterior pairs are weaker than two medial ones; ocellar setae strong, longer than orbital setae. Abdominal tergum 6 is 0.65 mm long, 0.6 times as long as tergum 5; tergo sternum 7 black, compressed dorso-ventrally and covered with blackish setulae; its length 0.40-0.48 mm; aculeus with rather large and acute serration; three spermathecae.

Body length of male 5.0–5.6; of female 5.8–6.0 mm.

Wing length 5.5–5.8 mm.

Remarks. As far as there are no other similar species in north-eastern China and Russian Far East, the type specimens of both *S. armifrons* and *S. alini*, are merely the two sexes of the same species, already known from large series of both males and females. The synonymy of these two species was supposed, but not introduced by Han, Wang and Kim (1994 a) for the formal reasons, as the type specimens of *S. armifrons* were not available for them. Genitalia of both sexes were figured in the latter work.

Vidalia rohdendorfi Richter

Richter, 1963; Kandybina, 1977; Foote, 1984; Ito, 1985 (*Vidalia*); Korneyev, 1995 (*Pseudina*). — *furialis* Ito, 1984 (*Vidalia*). — *rohdendorfi*: Ito, Tamaki, 1995 (*Vidalia*) (misspelling). — *brevialis*: Ito, Tamaki, 1995 (*Vidalia*). — ? *brevialis* Ito, 1985 (*Vidalia*).

Material. Type: *V. rohdendorfi*: Holotype: ♂: Russia: Prim.: «ст. Иманьпо, 15.VII 1914 (Емельянов)» [Иман'по station... Emelyanov] (ZISP) (examined); *V. furialis*: Holotype: ♂: Japan: "Sinano, Sigakōgen", 8. VIII 1981 (H. Hara) (UOP) (examined). Non-type material. Prim.: Kamenushka, 5.08.1984, 25.08.1987, Kievka, 7.09.1980, 7 ♂; 3 ♀ (Shatalkin) (ZMUM; SIZK) (dissected).

Remarks. Genitalia of both sexes were figured by Korneyev (1995). Preliminary phylogenetic analysis shows, that this species belongs to a sister-group either to all the other genera of the *Vidalia* group (*Chenacidiella* Shiraki, *Hoplandromyia* Bezzi and *Vidalia* R.-D.) or at least to the two latest. Dr. Xingjian Wang (in preparation) is supposed to establish a new genus for this species. *V. furialis* was described from two teneral specimens, otherwise fitting close *V. rohdendorfi*, and for this synonymized by Korneyev (1995). Ito and Tamaki (1995) synonymized *V. rohdendorfi* with *V. brevisalis*, but this must be accepted with some precaution, as both the head bristling and the wing pattern, though similar, have some minor differences (see Ito, 1985), not observed within the series before me. It may be either individual variability, or the characters of taxonomic significance, and I place *V. brevisalis* into the list of synonymy with a query mark.

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